

Acid-catalyzed hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid

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Abstract : The kinetics of hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid have been studied from 0.9 to 10.8 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ in 10/90 (v/v) *n*-propanol-water medium at 55 °C. The rate of reaction increases initially with increasing acidity, reaches a maximum and then decreases. After that at high acidities there is steep increase in reaction rate. The effect of temperature on the rate of hydrolysis has been studied. Activation parameters have been calculated. Bimolecular nature has been supported by Hammett, Zucker-Hammett, Bunnett, Bunnett-Olsen and Arrhenius activation parameters etc.

Keywords : Kinetics, temperature effect, molecularity, *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid.

Introduction

N-Substituted hydroxamic acid have been found to react with both proteins and nucleic acids¹ and their derivatives fulfill a variety of important role in analytical, biological and medicinal fields such as drug delivery system, iron-transport and DNA cleavage etc.¹. Hydroxamic acids have acquired phenomenal importance because of their current use in nuclear fuel reprocessing², pharmaceuticals³, solvent extraction^{4,5} and spectrophotometric determination of metals particularly using concentrated acid solution^{6,7}. Hydroxamic acids are weak organic acids⁸ with a wide variety of applications such as commercial flotation reagents in extractive metallurgy, as inhibitors for copper corrosion, as antifungal agents, as food additives⁹⁻¹². Particular attention has been devoted to the biological¹³⁻¹⁵ and chemical aspects of hydroxamic acids as well as to their potential clinical use as novel therapeutic agents^{16,17}. The chemical kinetic data of the hydrolysis reaction provides a judicious and rational basis for the search of new analytical reagents.

Experimental

N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) was prepared by the standard method^{18,19}. Its purity was tested by melting point and also by IR spectral analysis. The ferric chloride solution used in the colorimetric procedure was freshly prepared by dissolving 44.0 g of anhydrous ferric

chloride in 1 L of distilled water containing 10 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. All kinetic measurements were carried out at 45 °C and 55 °C. The concentration of PBHA was monitored spectrophotometrically²⁰ employing a Spekol instrument at 520 nm.

Results and discussion

Hydrolysis of PBHA has been kinetically investigated from 0.9 to 10.8 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ at 55 °C in 10/90 (v/v) *n*-propanol-water medium. It can be seen from the result that, the rate of reaction increases initially with increasing acidity, reaches a maximum and then decreases. After that at high acidities there is steep increase in reaction rate. The maximum is a consequence of opposing effects of increasing protonation and decreasing water activity. At low acidity, increasing acid concentration increased hydrolysis rate by raising the concentration of protonated substrates²¹. But as the acidity becomes sufficient to convert a large fraction of substrate into the protonated form, increasing acid concentration has little effect on the rate of hydrolysis. A new factor now becomes important, decrease in the activity of water with increasing acidity. The ionized form of hydroxamic acid is responsible for the increase in rate constant. The hydrolysis proceeds via conjugate acid species with N-C=O bond fission. Pseudo-first order rate constants determined by first order equa-

tion have been summarized in Table 1 and shown in Fig. 1. *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid undergoes hydrolysis in sulphuric acid solution to give carboxylic acid and *N*-phenylhydroxylamine (Scheme 1).

Table 1. Kinetic rate data for the hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA)

H ₂ SO ₄ (mol dm ⁻³)	pH	k _e × 10 ⁻⁴ (min ⁻¹)	4 + log k _e
0.9	0.96	21.8	1.34
1.8	0.94	29.9	1.48
2.7	0.84	41.5	1.62
3.6	0.75	54.1	1.73
4.5	0.68	60.5	1.78
5.4	0.61	65.8	1.82
6.3	0.54	57.0	1.76
7.2	0.48	46.1	1.66
8.1	0.41	36.2	1.56
9.0	0.38	46.5	1.67
9.5	0.34	61.4	1.79
9.9	0.33	92.8	1.97
10.8	0.28	174.7	2.24

Because hydroxamic acids are not soluble in water, a 10/90 (v/v) *n*-propanol-water medium is used. The above reaction showed a first-order rate dependence on substrate, and pseudo-first order rate constants were obtained at several sulfuric acid concentrations which are summarized in Table 1.

Molecularity :

Molecularity of a solvolytic reaction has been determined using Zucker-Hammett^{22,23} hypothesis. The hypothesis consists of two parts. The first part is the plot of log rate constant against -H₀. The slope = 0.18 of the plot is far from unity, indicating the absence of unimolecular hydrolysis. The kinetic rate data for this plot has been summarized in Table 2. The second part of hypothesis deals with the plot between log rate constant and log acid molarities which gives a slope = 0.72 clearly indicating the bimolecularity of the reaction.

The slope values ω and ω* obtained from Bunnett plots (12.9 and 1.27) indicate that the reaction is bimo-

Fig. 1. Plot of 4 + log k_e versus H₂SO₄ mol dm⁻³ for the acidic hydrolysis of PBHA.

Scheme 1

Table 2. Hammett and Zucker-Hammett plot data for the hydrolysis of PBHA

H ₂ SO ₄ (M)	log C _H ⁺	-H ₀	k _e × 10 ⁻⁴	4 + log k _e
1.8	0.25	0.68	29.9	1.48
2.7	0.43	1.14	41.5	1.62
3.6	0.56	1.62	54.1	1.73
4.5	0.65	2.08	60.5	1.78
5.4	0.73	2.50	65.8	1.82
6.3	0.80	3.00	57.0	1.79
7.2	0.86	3.44	46.1	1.66
8.1	0.91	3.90	36.2	1.56
9.0	0.95	-	46.5	1.67
9.5	0.98	-	61.4	1.79
9.9	0.99	-	92.8	1.97
10.8	1.03	-	174.7	2.24

(Eyring equation) which produces values for ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger together with their standard deviations. The values at different acidities are shown in Table 4. The ΔG^\ddagger values do not vary greatly with acid concentration. The change in ΔS^\ddagger implies that a change from a more to a less-restricted transition state is occurring as the acidity is increased (or as $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is decreased).

Conclusion :

Hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) has been found via conjugate acid species with N-C=O bond fission. Bimolecular nature of hydrolysis has been supported by different parameters such as Hammett, Zucker-Hammett, Bunnett, Bunnett-Olsen and Arrhenius activation parameters etc.

Table 3. Bunnett, Bunnett-Olsen data for hydrolysis of PBHA

H ₂ SO ₄ (M)	4 + log k _e - log C _H ⁺	4 + log k _e + H ₀	-log C _H ⁺	-log a _{H₂O}
1.8	1.23	0.80	0.43	0.02
2.7	1.19	0.48	0.71	0.04
3.6	1.17	0.11	1.06	0.07
4.5	1.13	-0.30	1.43	0.11
5.4	1.09	-0.68	1.77	0.16
6.3	0.96	-1.24	2.20	0.21
7.2	0.80	-1.78	2.58	0.28
8.1	0.65	-2.34	2.99	-

Table 4. Activation parameters for the hydrolysis of PBHA

H ₂ SO ₄ (mol dm ⁻³)	E _a	log A		ΔS [‡]		ΔH [‡]		ΔG [‡]	
		45 °C	55 °C	45 °C	55 °C	45 °C	55 °C	45 °C	55 °C
5.4	17.6	7.70	7.70	-23.3	-23.3	16.9	16.9	24.3	24.6
6.3	19.3	8.90	8.90	-18.1	-18.1	18.7	18.7	24.5	24.6
7.2	21.5	10.2	10.2	-12.1	-12.1	20.8	20.8	24.7	24.8

lecular in nature²⁴. Bunnett-Olsen parameter i.e. Φ is obtained from the plot between $\log k_e + H_0$ and $-\log C_{\text{H}^+} + H_0$. The value of $\Phi = 0.18$ which is in favour of the fact that water activity is playing an important role in deciding the rate at higher acidic concentration. Bunnett, Bunnett-Olsen plots data are summarized in Table 3.

Activation parameters :

It can be seen from the result that the magnitude of the Arrhenius parameters falls in the range of bimolecular reaction (Table 4). The temperature dependence of the rate constants of the hydrolysis reaction was analyzed by a least square procedure using a computer program

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